

Frontotemporal dementia is a complex disorder with a wide spectrum of clinical symptoms. Personalized medicine and gene therapy are promising strategies for treatment

Moataz Dowaidar^{1,2}

¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia.

²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage (IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia,

Abstract. Frontotemporal dementia is an uncommon and complex sickness with a wide spectrum of clinical symptoms, making drug development for the condition challenging. Frontal and temporal lobe responsibilities, as well as the level to which these activities are affected in certain diseases, contribute to clinical heterogeneity. Unfortunately, the available data on symptomatic treatments is drawn from limited case studies and RCTs, which include persons with the same FTD diagnosis. Advances in the identification of new FTD treatments demand the construction of huge clinical networks that are built on collaborative, multicenter research. One of the primary drawbacks of the present studies is the variety of the assessment instruments utilized, such as the FBI, Cambridge Behavioral Inventory, NPI, and BEHAVE-AD, some of which were not originally established for FTD but were first validated for other kinds of dementia, such as AD. The FBI was shown to have high sensitivity and specificity in discriminating between bvFTD and non-FTD, whereas the NPI score did not. The new definition of Alzheimer's disease was changed from a clinical diagnostic to a biomarker-based diagnostic, although we are still a long way from providing a scientific description of FTD. In the future, there might be an increased likelihood of recognizing symptoms or signs in clinical studies because of a revision to the criteria of FTD. Treatment techniques should be customized to individual patient subgroups or mutation carriers. Currently, as a treatment for FTD-tau, antisense oligonucleotide inhibition of MAPT, tau phosphorylation inhibition, microtubule stability, and inhibition of tau aggregation are all being investigated. It is possible to inhibit TDP-43 aggregation, enhance progranulin levels, activate the autophagy-lysosome system, or modify the ubiquitin-proteasome system in FTD-TDP. Despite these breakthroughs, the etiology and genetics of FTD remain unclear. Additional genetic pathways and loci associated with immune dysregulation and inflammation have recently been discovered, furthering the search for possible treatment targets. Also, knowing who the mutation carriers are early on allows researchers to test disease-modifying drugs earlier, when cognitive problems may still be reversible. Research gaps in the etiology and clinical characterization of FTD should be resolved, as well as the production of precise biomarkers and specialized evaluation methodologies. Desharnais and colleagues have created a checklist to assist standardize future FTD clinical trials and boost the probability of successful findings.

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1. Introduction

After Alzheimer's disease (AD), frontotemporal dementia (FTD) is the second most prevalent form of early-onset dementia, with an incidence of 0.8/100,000 among all dementias (1-2). These figures are regarded to represent an underestimate of the real epidemiology of the condition; the diagnosis is frequently missed due to behavioral clinical symptoms that are similar to those of other mental diseases (3).

FTD is thought to constitute a broad spectrum of neurodegenerative illnesses, based on recent breakthroughs in our knowledge of its mechanism. When the cellular inclusion bodies contain tau proteins (FTD-tau), FTD belongs to a family of neurodegenerative illnesses known as tauopathies (4). The condition is classified as FTD-TDP when these inclusions include TAR DNA binding protein 43 kDa-TDP-43 (5). FTD-fused in sarcoma (FTD-FUS) refers to ubiquitinated inclusions, neuronal intermediate filament inclusions, and basophilic

inclusion bodies that are immunoreactive for the FUS (6).

FTD has several clinical manifestations, including a behavioral variation (bvFTD) (7) and two language variations classified under the primary progressive aphasia (PPA) category (8). From a genetic standpoint, the disorder's high heritability can be attributed to numerous discovered autosomal dominant mutations. The most prevalent cause of genetic FTD is an enlargement of the chromosome 9 open reading frame 72 (C9orf72) gene, which is followed by the granulin (GRN) gene and finally the microtubule-associated protein tau (MAPT) gene (9). According to research, heredity varies depending on the clinical phenotype: roughly 50% of individuals with bvFTD have a significant family history, compared to 10% of patients with PPA (9).

Behavioral, verbal, cognitive, and motor symptoms of frontotemporal dementia have all been studied, and numerous therapies have been tried. There is currently no disease-modifying therapy for FTD. The present treatments are symptomatic in character, with little clinical effectiveness and a wide range of adverse effects. Because there is no FDA-approved therapy for this difficult illness, non-pharmacological behavioral therapies focusing on disease-specific behaviors and maintained capabilities in individuals with FTD are frequently required in addition to addressing carers' concern (10).

2. FTD bvFTD Clinical Variants

bvFTD is the most frequent clinical subtype of FTD, accounting for over half of all FTD cases in the United States and Europe (3). A large progressive alteration in personality and behavior from the premorbid baseline is a common clinical finding (12). Loss of inhibition (offensive remarks, inappropriate social behavior, and poor judgment), apathy, loss of empathy (often noticed by caregivers as a coldness towards individuals' feelings), hyperorality (altered food preferences, binge eating, or consumption of inedible foods), and compulsive behaviors such as stereotyped speech and repetitive gestures are all examples of typical behavioral changes. Disinhibition and obsessive behaviors lessen as the disease progresses, whereas apathy increases dramatically, indicating a gradual degradation of the medial frontal cortex. Apathy may manifest in a variety of ways and is sometimes misdiagnosed as depression. Affective apathy is characterized by indifference, whereas motor apathy is characterized by a diminished desire to move or total movement (17).

Parkinsonism may potentially be linked to advanced Parkinson's disease. Approximately 20% of patients with bvFTD develop motor neuron disease (MND), which includes upper motor neuron indications (hyper-reflexia and spasticity) and lower motor neuron indications (muscle atrophy and fasciculations) (18). The Worldwide Behavioral Variant FTD Criteria Consortium (7) released the international consensus criteria for bvFTD.

3. PPA (Public-Private-Partner

Progressive speech and language impairment (aphasia) is the major symptom of basic progressive aphasia, which has no substantial cognitive, physical, or behavioral components. It shows up as difficulties with word finding, usage, understanding, and sentence structure in ordinary conversations and speech and language examinations (19). With the exception of aspects relevant to language, daily activities are preserved (e.g., difficulty using the telephone). The language-dominant (typically left) hemisphere suffers the most from neurodegeneration. The distribution of neuronal loss across the language network determines agrammatic, semantic, and logopenic variations. The first two variations have been linked to FTD pathology and are discussed more below, whereas the logopenic variation has been linked to AD pathology and is discussed more below. Degeneration of other cognitive areas may develop in later stages of the illness, while language remains the most impacted (8).

4. PPA with a grammatical error

It is also known as the non-fluent variant PPA (nfvPPA), which is a motor speech deficiency that causes articulatory problems. Stopping speech with speech-sound problems, distortions, and agrammatism in language output are some of the clinical signs (8). Iterative exercises reveal apraxia of speech, particularly in vowel production. Atrophy of the left inferior frontal gyrus and posterior fronto-insular areas corresponds to such impairments (20).

Simple phrases or single words are shielded from speech comprehension, while complicated phrase patterns with complicated syntax become visible. Object knowledge is also not taken into account (8). While early illness is limited to expressive language impairments, the disease progresses to a more widespread dementia with loss of autonomy in everyday tasks approximately 6–7 years after beginning. Behavioral abnormalities, MND, and corticobasal degeneration can all occur in certain people (21).

svPPA

The semantic variant FTD (svPPA), also known as the "temporal variant FTD," is marked by deficiencies in single-word understanding and object identification. Fluency, repetition, syntax, and grammar all stay the same. The capacity to grasp single object words is weakened early on, but the entire sentence comprehension is intact. Low-frequency words (giraffe) lose comprehension before high-frequency terms (dog). As the illness advances, understanding becomes increasingly compromised on a global level. Patients may develop dyslexia or dysgraphia as a result of a loss of semantic information of particular words (object features) (22). The language-based symptoms are caused by neurodegeneration of the left temporal lobe. Involvement of the right temporal lobe causes poor identification of known and renowned faces, as well as changes in eating preferences such as food limits (as opposed to binge eating in bvFTD) and strange food choices (23). Patients with the left temporal lobe variation have heightened right-side functions such as visual attention, which can lead to visual compulsions (repetitive jigsaw puzzle activities and brightly colored objects collection). Verbal compulsions involving words and symbols (e.g., writing notes, letters, and phone numbers) develop in people with the right temporal lobe variation (3). Episodic memory loss and behavioral abnormalities occur as the illness spreads from the front temporal lobes to the mesial temporal and orbitofrontal cortices (3, 24).

5. Current Symptomatic Treatments for FTD Efficacy

Treatment for FTD symptoms is customized and dependent on the patient's symptom profile (25). We examine the effectiveness of currently available therapies for neurotransmitter abnormalities based on data from clinical trials. The bulk of FTD research has discovered a serotonergic deficiency that appears to be more postsynaptic than presynaptic, as well as dopamine dysregulation in the basal ganglia, whereas the cholinergic and noradrenergic systems appear to be unaffected (26).

Antidepressants**SSRIs**

SSRIs such as citalopram, sertraline, fluoxetine, paroxetine, and fluvoxamine have been examined for the treatment of disinhibition, stereotypies, dietary changes, and hypersexual behaviors in individuals with FTD, with variable results based primarily on uncontrolled research. SSRIs, on the other hand, have been utilized as a first-line therapy off-label.

In a 3-month open-label investigation of 11 individuals with FTD, fluoxetine, sertraline, and paroxetine showed improvement in disinhibition, depressive symptoms, carbohydrate seeking, and compulsions in at least half of the individuals (27).

In eight individuals with FTD identified by the Lund and Manchester criteria, paroxetine (at a dosage of 20 mg daily for 14 months) resulted in a statistically significant improvement in behavioral symptoms, with no subgroups specified. The Behavioral Pathology in Alzheimer's Disease BEHAVE-AD rating scale (change of 13.075 points over piracetam 2400 mg/day; $p < 0.01$), the neuropsychiatric interview (Neuropsychiatric Inventory (NPI)) total scores (change of 8.25 points over baseline; $p < 0.05$; by 13.25 points over piracetam; $p < 0.01$), and the Cornell Scale for Depression (change of 3.15 points over baseline; $p < 0.05$). Paroxetine at a dosage of 40 mg daily failed to show a statistically significant change in the NPI or the Cambridge Behavioral Inventory in ten recruited persons with bvFTD in a 4-week, placebo-controlled cross-over randomized controlled trial (RCT). On the contrary, accuracy on the paired associates learning test, reversal learning, and a delayed pattern recognition task were all reduced (29).

A larger dose of paroxetine (40 mg twice a day) was observed to reduce or eliminate repetitive and ritualistic behaviors in 75 percent of patients with FTD (16 bvFTD, 10 nfVPPA, and 9 svPPA) in another observational trial of 35 patients with FTD (16 bvFTD, 10 nfVPPA, and 9 svPPA) (8 out of 11 patients). Patients' primary care doctors or neurologists ordered this therapy based on subjective factors given by caregivers. Improvements were reported based on caregiver reports or physician observations. There were no NPI measurements taken before or after therapy (30).

In an observational study of 18 individuals with bvFTD, sertraline (doses between 50 and 100 mg daily) significantly reduced verbal and motor stereotypies as judged by the Abnormal Involuntary Movement Scale (31). In a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled cross-over research including 12 right-handed individuals with bvFTD, citalopram (a single dose of 30 mg) was evaluated for the treatment of disinhibition. A total of 20 healthy older people were also used as controls. The Go/No-Go task was used to measure the capacity to suppress incorrect reactions. Magnetoencephalography/electroencephalography and cerebral

magnetic resonance imaging were also performed on the participants. Controls performed a magnetoencephalography/electroencephalography technique in one session without citalopram providing normative data for this task. Cortical sources related to effective inhibition in controls were found as the right inferior frontal gyrus and anterior temporal lobe. In this study, citalopram raised the No-Go P3 signal (inhibition) in the patients, as well as the evoked response in the right inferior frontal gyrus, when compared to placebo therapy. However, there was no effect on the accuracy or response time of the patients. These data support the concept that individuals with FTD have serotonin dysfunction in the prefrontal cortex, which might be improved with SSRIs (32).

Citalopram was given at a dosage of 30 mg (single dose/challenge test) in another research, followed by a 6-week open-label phase during which it was titrated from 10 mg to 40 mg daily depending on tolerability. The patients in this study were diagnosed with FTD according to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 4th Edition criteria and exhibited substantial behavioral symptoms as evidenced by an NPI score of less than eight. A total of 15 patients with a mean age of 67.2 8.5 years were separated into three groups: 12 with bvFTD, 2 with nvPPA, and 1 with svPPA. Over the course of 6 weeks, citalopram medication resulted in a substantial drop in NPI for behavioral symptoms ($p = 0.004$), disinhibition ($p = 0.029$), irritability ($p = 0.003$), and depression ($p = 0.045$), with no effect on cognition or activities of daily living (33). In an 80-year-old male patient with bvFTD, citalopram was demonstrated to significantly alleviate obsessive compulsive symptoms with a minor overall improvement in total NPI scores at a dosage of 20 mg daily delivered over the course of a year (34).

Fluvoxamine (doses between 50 and 150 mg daily) was tested in 12 individuals with FTD (three subtypes) who had a mean Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) of 13.8 9.5 in a 12-week open-label experiment. At week 12, the NPI overall score and the abnormal motor behavior NPI subcomponent (both $p < 0.05$) showed a statistically significant reduction in behavioral abnormalities as compared to baseline ($p < 0.05$ for both). In addition, as compared to baseline, stereotyped behaviors improved dramatically as measured by the Stereotypy Rating Inventory overall score ($p < 0.01$). Each component of the Stereotypy Rating Inventory (eating, wandering, speaking, motions, and daily rhythm; $p < 0.05$) was shown to be considerably improved. According to the MMSE (35), there was no change in cognition.

Trazodone is a narcotic that is used to

Trazodone is a serotonin (5-HT₂) antagonist and reuptake inhibitor that functions as an atypical serotonergic antidepressant. Histamine and alpha-1-adrenergic receptors are likewise blocked. 31 patients fulfilling the Lund and Manchester Group criteria for FTD, with a score of 13 on the Frontal Behavioral Dysfunction Scale and a total score on the NPI > 8 , were involved in a 6-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled cross-over research (no subtypes specified). Trazodone at 150–300 mg was linked to a substantial reduction in the NPI total score ($p = 0.028$) in 16 out of 31 individuals. Trazodone provided the highest behavioral effect ($p = 0.04$) for individuals with more severe eating disorders at baseline, according to a multivariate analysis (36).

After the double-blind experiment ended, a follow-up extension study was undertaken with regular evaluations of the NPI total scores at a dosage of 300 mg of trazodone daily. Two patients died from causes unrelated to the study medicine, resulting in a drop-out rate of 23% within the first 12 months and 15% after 12 months. Two patients were institutionalized and never followed up on, while the other two dropped out and refused to be followed up on. The remaining 16 patients were followed for an average of 36.7 months (11.5). The NPI total score in these participants was considerably lower during follow-up than at baseline ($p < 0.0005$). There was no effect on cognition (37).

A suggestion In people with FTD, SSRIs can help with agitation, disinhibition, stereotypies, obsessions/compulsions, eating disorders, and sadness (grade C; level of evidence 4). Another antidepressant, trazodone, can be used to treat neuropsychiatric symptoms at a dosage of 150–300 mg per day (grade B; level of evidence 2b). Large RCTs are needed to corroborate these findings, particularly the fact that the serotonergic abnormalities reported in FTD are postsynaptic, casting doubt on the role/impact of SSRIs.

6. Treatments for Dementia

Inhibitors of Cholinesterase

There was a statistically significant reduction of 15.1 4.2 points on the NPI ($p < 0.001$ vs baseline and control) and 4.4 3.3 points on the BEHAVE-AD ($p < 0.001$ vs baseline and control) in an open-label study involving 40 patients with FTD (unspecified type) followed for a year taking rivastigmine 3–9 mg/day. Rivastigmine also decreased caregiver burnout, as measured by a drop of 16 7.1 points on the Relatives' Stress Scale ($p < 0.001$).

versus baseline and control) after 12 months of therapy. The MMSE, on the other hand, showed no effect on cognitive deterioration (38). In a group of four male patients with FTD (unspecified subtype), both donepezil and rivastigmine were linked to improvements in the MMSE and the clock-drawing test, compared to no/minimal improvement in female patients ($n = 5$). Other factors, such as the participants' age, might have contributed to the sex disparity, according to the researchers (39).

In 36 individuals with FTD, galantamine (doses 16–24 mg daily) was studied in an 18-week open-label study followed by an 8-week double-blind placebo-controlled experiment (both bvFTD and PPA). Changes in the Frontal Behavioral Inventory (FBI), the Aphasia Quotient of the Western Aphasia Battery, and the Clinical Global Impressions of Improvement (CGI-I) and Severity from week 18 to week 26 were the key effectiveness evaluations (CGI-S). Only eight bvFTD patients and 10 PPA patients completed the whole experiment, including the RCT phase. In the bvFTD group, galantamine was not shown to be efficacious. In the placebo-controlled withdrawal phase, the CGI-S was in favor of galantamine in the PPA subgroup ($p = 0.009$), but this was not significant when the Bonferroni correction was performed for multiple comparisons (40). It has been suggested that linguistic variations of FTD may have a cholinergic deficit relative to the bvFTD subtype, prompting researchers to look at this class of medicines in certain phenotypes of the condition, such as PPA (41).

Another research compared 12 patients with bvFTD who took donepezil (10 mg daily for 6 months) to 12 controls. The medicine vs. placebo assignment was not random and relied on the permission of patients and caregivers. Both physicians and caregivers who were not blind to diagnosis or therapy completed the MMSE scores, the Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR) scale, and the FTD Inventory. The MMSE and CDR scores of treated patients did not change significantly at 6 months, but they had poorer FTD Inventory difference scores between baseline and 6 months ($p 0.05$).

In this sample of patients, caregivers reported more instances of socially unacceptable acts or intrusive behaviors (inappropriate comments, approaching others) as well as more stereotyped and repeated behaviors (42). Delirium was also reported in a 43-year-old male patient with bvFTD who developed 2 weeks after starting donepezil (10 mg/day); the disorientation was reversible when the drug was stopped (43).

7. Memantine/NMDA-Receptor Antagonist

Two randomized controlled trials looked at the effects of memantine (10 mg twice a day) in individuals with bvFTD. The Clinician's Interview-Based Impression of Change Plus Caregiver Input was the major endpoint in the first trial, and there were no significant changes between the memantine ($n = 23$) and placebo ($n = 26$) groups 52 weeks after baseline ($p = 0.4458$). In the qualitative analysis, ten patients in the memantine group performed worse on the Clinician's Interview-Based Impression of Change Plus Caregiver Input ratings compared to 17 in the placebo group (44), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.142$).

Patients with bvFTD and svPPA were included in the second trial, which was a multicenter, 26-week RCT. Antidepressants were allowed provided the dose had been steady for a month previous to study admission. Cholinesterase inhibitors were not allowed. The NPI and the Clinician's Global Impression of Change were the primary outcomes. The CDR total of boxes and the MMSE were among the secondary outcomes, although they were not the only ones. Eighty-one patients (64 with bvFTD and 17 with svPPA) were given either memantine ($n = 39$, with 37 completers) or placebo ($n = 42$, with 39 completers). On the NPI or the Clinician's Global Impression of Change, there were no statistically significant changes (p -values of 0.24 and 0.9, respectively). On any of the secondary outcome measures, there was no evidence of a favorable impact. On measures of naming and processing speed, the memantine group performed worse than the placebo group in neuropsychological tests (45).

Insufficient sample sizes may have contributed to the negative outcomes of these RCTs. A recent meta-analysis of these two studies tried to increase the power to detect a difference by expanding the sample size (130 individuals). The CGI, MMSE, NPI, and Zarit Burden Inventory total scores did not change significantly between the memantine and placebo therapy groups. The CGI scores, on the other hand, were approaching significance ($p = 0.06$), prompting researchers to pursue bigger trials in this direction (46).

Recommendation: If you're looking for a unique way to express yourself, Cholinesterase inhibitors are not advised for people with bvFTD who are experiencing cognitive deterioration (grade C; level of evidence 4). Galantamine (16–24 mg daily) may be especially useful in the PPA variation (grade B; level of evidence 2b) and deserves more research.

In all forms of FTD, memantine (20 mg daily) is not indicated, and it has even been linked to decreasing cognitive functioning (grade A; level of evidence 1a).

Oxytocin is a hormone that is produced by the body.

Oxytocin is a neuropeptide that has been linked to social behavior and cognition in humans. Its significance in altering neuronal pathways underpinning emotional processing in the frontal and temporal lobes, notably the amygdala and insular lobe, has been established in neuroimaging studies (47, 48).

Twenty patients with bvFTD were given one dosage of 24 IU intranasal oxytocin or placebo and subsequently performed emotion detection tests in a double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized cross-over study. Caregivers were also asked to complete behavioral assessments eight hours and one week after the medicine was administered. When compared to placebo and baseline, there was a substantial improvement in NPI ratings after 8 hours but not at 1 week (49).

A more recent dose-finding RCT was done, with 23 patients with bvFTD or svPPA receiving three dosages (24, 48, or 72 IU) twice daily for one week. The oxytocin group showed non-significant improvements in subscales of the NPI, FBI, and Interpersonal Reactivity Index, which measures empathy, as compared to the placebo group. Informants also mentioned improved patient-caregiver relationships. In terms of efficacy on empathy and indifference assessments, the higher dose of 72 IU appeared to be the most promising (50).

A suggestion Intranasal oxytocin (24 to 72 IU) has been shown to improve empathy and caregiver-patient contact (grade B; level 2b). This finding will need to be confirmed in larger, more powerful RCTs.

Lithium.

Lithium is a well-known mood stabilizer that is used to treat bipolar illness. Because of its inhibitory effects on glycogen synthase kinase-3 and tau phosphorylation, lithium has been found to be neuroprotective in tauopathies such as AD and FTD at modest dosages (51). These effects were subsequently discovered to be substantial in people who have particular genetic variants in the UNC13 presynaptic protein, which are present in FTD and other mental illnesses (52). Lithium taken at dosages ranging from 300 to 1200 mg daily alleviated behavioral abnormalities, particularly agitation with or without psychotic symptoms, in a case series of three individuals with bvFTD or svPPA. Lithium values in the blood varied from 0.4 to 0.8 mmol/L (53).

A 12-week phase II, randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind study (NCT02862210) is currently recruiting 60 patients with FTD who will receive 150 mg of lithium daily titrated up to 600 mg daily depending on tolerance. Changes in agitation and aggressiveness, as judged by these NPI subscales at week 12, are the major end measures.

A suggestion Lithium (dosage to be modified according to serum concentrations) may be prescribed to people with FTD who are agitated (grade C; level of evidence 4).

In a 73-year-old male patient with bvFTD, aripiprazole (10 mg/day, for 13 months) was reported to partially restore altered frontal glucose metabolism and alleviate behavioral abnormalities, particularly apathy (54). In two instances with bvFTD, different dosages of aripiprazole (18 and 30 mg/day for two weeks) were demonstrated to ameliorate inappropriate sexual behavior and vocalizations (55, 56).

Olanzapine was evaluated in a case series of 17 individuals with bvFTD who were followed for 24 months and had a mean age of 69.5 3.5 years. The dominating symptoms, as shown by NPI and BEHAVE scores, were stereotypical behavior, perseveration, mood changes, and diminished interest; these were closely connected with caregiver distress (p 0.01). An average daily dose of 3 0.71 mg of olanzapine was shown to be effective in treating behavioral problems. There was a statistically significant reduction in delusions (p 0.01) and other behavioral abnormalities, as measured by NPI and BEHAVE scores (p 0.01 and 0.05, respectively). When compared to baseline, caregiver stress was also considerably decreased (p 0.01) (57). To corroborate this conclusion, double-blind placebo-controlled studies are necessary. Quetiapine at a dose of 250 mg in the morning and 500 mg at bedtime improved subjective reports of agitation without exacerbating parkinsonism in a case series of three patients with FTD (unspecified subtype) (30), while risperidone (6 mg daily) improved psychosis in a 42-year-old woman with bvFTD (58).

A suggestion In individuals with any subtype of FTD, antipsychotics can be used with caution to treat psychosis and severe instances of agitation (grade C; level of evidence 4). Clinicians should be aware of the FDA's warning concerning the increased risk of death associated with their usage in cognitively challenged people.

8. Antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) are prescription medications used to treat epilepsy.

The use of antiepileptic medications in FTD is little documented. In a 78-year-old male patient with Kluver–Bucy syndrome and bvFTD who was having inappropriate sexual behavior that did not respond to paroxetine 40 mg/day, a successful response to carbamazepine 800 mg/day (serum concentration of 6 mg/L) was described. Before the patient was lost to follow-up, the therapeutic benefits continued for 6 months (59).

Topiramate is an antiepileptic medication that suppresses appetite. It was observed to diminish stereotyped and obsessive eating habits in various FTD patients (bvFTD and PPA) with clear lobar atrophy involvement, as measured by the eating behavior questionnaire, at dosages of 100–150 mg given for 6 weeks. In a 53-year-old male patient, topiramate at a dosage of 100 mg daily for 7 months was observed to diminish alcohol use disorder without impacting other clinical symptoms of bvFTD (including obsessional behavior) (61). Valproic acid has been used seldom and has yet to be demonstrated effective (62).

Topiramate (100–150 mg daily) is an antiepileptic medicine that can be used to treat eating disorders and alcohol use disorder in people with FTD (grade C; level of evidence 4).

9. Medications that are anti-parkinsonian

Bromocriptine is a dopamine agonist that has been proven to increase speech output in non-fluent aphasia following left hemisphere infarctions (63). Six participants with nfvPPA with an average age of 66.8 years were given 7.5 mg of bromocriptine three times daily for seven weeks in a cross-over RCT. Only narrative language was enhanced as measured by mean utterance length, but there was no statistically significant effect on overall language functions (such as naming and word fluency) in this short experiment (64).

In two out of three individuals with FTD, carbidopa/levodopa 25/250 mg administered four times daily was demonstrated to ameliorate parkinsonian symptoms, particularly stiffness and bradykinesia (unspecified subtypes). Carbidopa/levodopa improved both speech and bradykinesia in one nfv-PPA instance. Furthermore, six out of nine PPA participants reacted to amantadine (100 mg, three times daily) in terms of speech fluency and alertness, which caregivers noted as well (30).

Recommendation: Bromocriptine (grade B; level of evidence 2b) or carbidopa/levodopa and amantadine can enhance speech fluency in FTD language variations (grade C; level of evidence 4). Carbidopa/levodopa with amantadine may help with bradykinesia and stiffness in people with Parkinson's disease (grade C; level of evidence 4).

10. The use of stimulants

Anatomopathological and biological studies both suggest a dopaminergic deficit/dysregulation in FTD, challenging the widely held idea that stimulant drugs may exacerbate FTD symptoms. Dextroamphetamine 20 mg/day was given for three weeks in a cross-over experiment (with quetiapine 150 mg/day) to eight individuals with bvFTD. When compared to baseline, the overall NPI score in the dextroamphetamine group was considerably lower ($p = 0.02$), but there was no significant difference between baseline and quetiapine, or between quetiapine and dextroamphetamine (65).

Immediate-release methylphenidate (10 mg twice a day) was proven to improve mood, affect (apathy), and impulsivity in a 72-year-old male patient with bvFTD. These favorable alterations were linked to an improvement in the frontotemporal portions of the left cortex's abnormally slowed cortical activity, as measured by quantitative electroencephalography (66). A single dosage of methylphenidate 40 mg had no effect on neuropsychological performance, including memory and attentional tests, conducted 90 minutes after the dosage, but dramatically reduced betting behaviors ($p = 0.0017$), which represent decision-making and risk-taking behaviors (67).

Recommendation: If you're looking for a unique way to express yourself, stimulants may help people with bvFTD improve their mood, apathy, and impulse control without increasing behavioral problems (grade C; level

of evidence 4).

11. Current Treatments for FTD Tolerance and Safety

Antidepressants are one of the best-tolerated FTD symptomatic therapies. In this demographic, SSRIs have been linked to nausea (32), weight loss, and sleepiness (33) for citalopram.

Diarrhea is another gastrointestinal adverse effect that caused one patient to stop using sertraline (27). Three out of every eight patients (37.5%) who took paroxetine had temporary nausea during the first 10 days of treatment, which went away on its own. There were no major side effects observed, and there was no change in heart rhythm or blood pressure (28). One patient in another paroxetine experiment stopped taking it due to increasing anxiety (27). Paroxetine has also been linked to headaches (30). Fluvoxamine was similarly well tolerated, with the exception of nausea/loss of appetite in one participant, which led to treatment cessation (35). When trazodone was compared to placebo, mild side effects were found: 11/26 individuals on trazodone felt weariness, dizziness, hypotension, and chilly extremities (36). The longest follow-up of individuals with FTD receiving trazodone was two years, and it revealed that hypotension was the most common adverse effect, which was treated with midodrine in four out of 26 individuals. This adverse event resulted in no patient discontinuing therapy (37).

Donepezil, like other cholinesterase inhibitors, has been proven to cause disorientation and aggravate behavioral problems. In individuals with FTD and concomitant MND, cholinesterase inhibitors are also linked to increased oral secretions, which contribute to aspiration (68).

In both RCTs with this medicine, memantine was well tolerated generally, with no statistically significant difference in all-cause discontinuation (46). It was linked to a larger number of cognitive adverse events (confusion, memory loss, language difficulties) and poor neurocognitive performance in one research (45). Except for small increases in hypersexual behaviors (one third of patients taking the medication versus 14 percent of placebo patients), intranasal oxytocin was shown to be safe and well tolerated in patients with FTD at all three dosages studied (24, 48, and 72 IU twice daily) (50).

Lithium was poorly tolerated and linked to an increased risk of falls, drowsiness, and tremor, particularly at high dosages (about 1200 mg/day) (53).

Antipsychotics should also be taken with caution in patients with FTD due to the FDA's boxed warning about an elevated risk of death and falls in people with dementia. Furthermore, because of pre-treatment nigrostriatal abnormalities, individuals with FTD are more vulnerable to extrapyramidal symptoms (parkinsonism and tardive dyskinesias) during antipsychotic therapy (69). Antipsychotic sensitivity has been demonstrated in individuals with FTD and C9orf72 expansion; certain side outcomes were permanent in certain cases even after medication removal (70). Lower potency antipsychotics, such as quetiapine, are favored for all of these reasons, especially in individuals with movement problems. Antipsychotics in general and depot formulations in particular should be avoided (69).

In addition, the most prevalent side effect recorded with olanzapine was somnolence (31%), followed by constipation (23%), dry mouth (11%), and fecal impaction (7%), all of which improved with dosage reduction. There were no significant side effects, clinical changes in vital signs, weight, or electrocardiographic measurements, or alterations in glucose metabolism observed with olanzapine (57).

The most prevalent adverse effect of stimulants is sleep problems. Methylphenidate raises blood pressure in general, but the differences in systolic and diastolic blood pressure were not statistically significant ($p = 0.075$) (67). One of the six people who took bromocriptine stopped using it due to a side effect called frustration intolerance (64). In this patient group, psychosis and vivid dreams prevented greater carbidopa/levodopa dose (30). Amantadine was linked to livedo reticularis, a reddish blue skin discoloration that became more noticeable at dosages of 200–300 mg per day (30). Finally, doctors should be aware of drug–drug interactions in people with FTD, particularly as they get older and develop polypharmacy (71).

FTD Treatment Options on the Rise

In terms of disease modification, research is underway to target the three primary genetic alterations linked to FTD.

12. The GRN Mutation Is Being Targeted

The GRN gene mutation causes haploinsufficiency of matching messenger RNA expression, resulting in lower quantities of progranulin protein in the plasma and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) (72, 73). Progranulin's specific actions are unknown; nevertheless, it is thought that this protein may have neurotrophic and synaptic effects on the central nervous system. In addition, people with GRN mutations have been discovered to have autoimmune diseases (74). Progranulin was shown to be involved in the control of inflammation in mouse models through antagonistic effects of tumor necrosis factor-(75). Huang et al. (76) established the involvement of progranulin in regulating aberrant microglia activation during aging in the same vein of neuroinflammation. Progranulin deficiency has been linked to complement activation and synaptic pruning by microglia, resulting in endo-lysosomal dysfunction and neurodegeneration (77). To reduce microglial toxicity and neurodegeneration, a novel treatment method includes inhibiting C1qa and C3 activation (76).

Another proposed treatment strategy is to use alkalizing medicines like chloroquine and amiodarone to boost or restore progranulin levels (78). A recent pilot trial of amiodarone in five individuals with FTD who were GRN mutation carriers found that it did not raise progranulin levels or modify the course of the disease (79). In an open-label, 8-week dose-finding phase I clinical study, the effects of nimodipine, a central nervous system-penetrant calcium channel blocker, on serum and CSF progranulin levels were investigated. The research included eight GRN mutation carriers, but progranulin levels did not decrease significantly (80).

FRM-0334 (FORUM pharmaceuticals) is a histone deacetylase inhibitor that affects gene function through epigenetic control. It enters the central nervous system and has been demonstrated to stimulate the transcription of the non-mutated copy of the gene, increasing progranulin levels (81). The trial's findings have yet to be made public (NCT02149160).

AL001 is a recombinant human anti-human sortilin (SORT1) monoclonal IgG1 developed by Alector in collaboration with Abbvie that has been demonstrated in phase I/II studies to restore plasma and CSF progranulin levels (Alector press release on phases Ib and 2 with AL001, 2020). A phase III, double-blind, placebo-controlled research examining the effectiveness and safety of AL001 in people who are at risk for or have FTD owing to heterozygous mutations in the progranulin gene will begin in July 2020. It's scheduled to be finished in October 2023. 180 individuals with FTD will get monthly intravenous injections of AL001 at a dose of 60 mg/kg for up to 18 months. The change in a combination of the Clinical Dementia Rating and the NACC FTLD-Sum of Boxes is the primary outcome (NCT04374136).

13. The C9ORF72 Gene Is Being Targeted

In both familial and sporadic FTD, the hexanucleotide GGGGCC repeat expansion in the noncoding region of the C9ORF72 gene appears to be the most common kind of genetic aberration. The actual mechanism responsible for neurodegeneration is currently unknown. The increase of function accomplished by the synthesis of hazardous RNA containing the GGGGCC repeat (82) appears to be one of the most plausible possibilities. Synthetic nucleic acids complementary to the C9ORF72 RNA transcript sequence are known as antisense oligonucleotides. They are expected to reduce neurodegeneration by inactivating the RNA foci of a target gene via direct binding or triggering RNase-mediated breakage (83, 84). Biogen, in collaboration with IONIS Pharmaceuticals, is testing BIIB080 as a targeted antisense oligonucleotide therapy for C9ORF72 hazardous aggregates (85).

Tau as a target

Tau, a microtubule-associated protein that forms insoluble filamentous inclusions that disrupt axonal transport control, microtubule formation, and microtubule stability, is being targeted aggressively (86). Despite the fact that tau and progranulin are both found on chromosome 17, their neurodegenerative processes appear to be distinct. Tau mutations appear to generate a toxic gain of function in both gray and white matter of multiple brain areas, with aberrant aggregations of both three and four microtubule-binding repeat pathogenic tau isoforms (87). Hyperphosphorylated tau builds up in the soma and dendrites of neurons, causing microtubule depolymerization and interfering with axonal transport. As a result of the mitochondrial dysfunction, harmful reactive oxygen species are produced, which promotes neurodegeneration (88). Tau has also been demonstrated to have features comparable to prions in terms of its ability to self-promote from cell to cell (89).

Inhibiting tau aggregation, lowering tau expression, preventing tau cleavage and spreading, boosting tau degradation, and stabilizing microtubules are all being studied (90). Anti-tau antibodies injected into multiple tau epitopes in tau transgenic mice models were related to lower tau pathology and both cognitive and functional improvement, indicating a delay in disease development (91,92,93).

Two more monoclonal humanized anti-tau antibodies are being studied in people with FTD/progressive supranuclear palsy, based on preclinical data: ABBV-8E12 (Abbvie) was tested in 30 patients with progressive supranuclear palsy/FTD at dosages ranging from 2.5 to 50 mg/kg and demonstrated a satisfactory tolerance and safety profile, advancing the product to phase II studies (94). In a sample of 65 healthy people, increasing dosages of BIIB092 (up to 4200 mg) administered as a single intravenous dosage showed a dose-dependent reduction of unbound N-terminal tau in CSF (95).

In bvFTD, tau aggregation inhibitors are being studied. A strong inhibitor of pathological aggregation of tau and TDP-43 proteins is leuco-methylthionium (LMT/TRx0237), a stabilized reduced form of methylthionium chloride. The FDA designated LMT as an orphan medication in 2018 for the treatment of FTD (96). On the Addenbrookes Cognitive Examination—Revised and the Functional Activities Questionnaire, a 52-week phase III clinical study utilizing LMT (100 mg/twice daily) failed to show any therapeutic effect. When compared to placebo, it likewise failed to slow the course of total brain atrophy. Because LMT causes urine to become blue, the placebo group was given 4 mg of LMT twice a day to keep them blind. Based on a previous phase II AD study with methylthionium chloride, which determined that 138 mg was the lowest efficacious dosage (97), this low dosage was not predicted to have any clinical impact. However, a pharmacokinetic analysis of exposure-response profiles and clinical and magnetic resonance imaging biomarker outcomes revealed that an 8 mg/day dose resulted in blood concentrations of 0.3–0.6 ng/mL, which were linked to clinical Addenbrookes Cognitive Examination—Revised and Functional Activities Questionnaire scales and magnetic resonance imaging volumetric outcomes. Surprisingly, larger plasma concentrations in the range of 7–14 ng/mL were related to poor outcomes in patients receiving the 200-mg/day dosage (98). When the larger dosage was compared to the lower 8-mg/day LMT dosage in AD studies, failure to fulfill main objectives was also noted (99).

Other medications targeting post-translational tau changes such as acetylation or microtubule stabilization are being investigated, although they are still in the early stages of clinical development (100).

14. Conclusions

Frontotemporal dementia is a rare and complicated ailment with a wide range of clinical symptoms, which makes planning successful clinical trials to find effective medication for this severe disease difficult (100). The intricate roles of the frontal and temporal lobes, as well as the amount to which these functions are compromised in diverse types of the disease, contribute to clinical heterogeneity. Unfortunately, the present data on symptomatic therapies is based on tiny uncontrolled studies (case reports and case series) and low-quality RCTs including people with the same FTD diagnosis. To overcome recruiting obstacles and increase sample sizes, advances in the discovery of medicines for FTD necessitate the creation of vast clinical networks based on multicenter collaborative projects. Another major limitation of the current trials is the heterogeneity of the tools used to assess behavioral outcomes, such as the FBI, Cambridge Behavioral Inventory, NPI, and BEHAVE-AD, some of which were not specifically designed for FTD but were first developed and validated for other types of dementias, such as AD (25). The FBI, for example, was shown to have high sensitivity and specificity (97 and 95 percent, respectively) in distinguishing between bvFTD and non-FTD, but the NPI score did not distinguish FTD from AD (101).

Individuals with FTD and their families require new tailored objectives that are clinically meaningful (100). Innovative assessments, such as the Multidomain Impairment Rating scale, have recently been created to address the clinical variability of FTD. It incorporates parts of the FTD-CDR scale, as well as a visuospatial domain, parkinsonism, MND, and other non-cognitive/non-behavioral features, to better characterize the disease's clinical spectrum (102). Disinhibition, apathy, perseveration, hyperorality, personal neglect, and loss of empathy are among the six dimensions explored by the DAPHNE scale (103). In addition, social cognition has been identified as a particular FTD outcome sign (104). Instruments like the Social Cognition and Emotional Assessment (105) and the Revised Self-Monitoring Scale are being investigated as prospective clinical endpoint measures for assessing socioemotional sensitivity in future FTD clinical studies (106).

While there has been a recent change in the definition of Alzheimer's disease from a purely clinical to a biomarker-based diagnosis (107), we are still a long way from defining a biological description of FTD based on particular biomarkers. In the future, a similar modification in the definition of FTD might assist to better confirm the diagnosis in research participants and raise the chances of identifying signals in clinical trials.

Biomarkers for FTD, like those for Alzheimer's disease, can be diagnostic and predictive, allowing researchers to assess staging and therapy responses. Combining biofluids and imaging measurements, in theory, can offer

the optimum combination of sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy, especially if data comes from large cohorts rather than small pilot studies, as is the case now (108). Data from positron emission tomography using (18) F-fluorodeoxyglucose, when combined with the clinical history, may improve the diagnosis accuracy of FTD. With a specificity of 97.6%, a sensitivity of 86%, and a positive probability ratio for FTD of 36.5, (18) F-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography is becoming more popular in clinical and research contexts (109).

Future clinical trials will benefit from the development of additional imaging and fluid biomarkers, as well as the use of new wearable technologies in the evaluation of clinical outcomes (100, 108, 110).

Precision medicine demands that treatment approaches should be tailored to specific patient subgroups or mutation bearers (70). Antisense oligonucleotide suppression of MAPT, inhibition of tau phosphorylation and acetylation, stability of microtubules, inhibition of tau aggregation, and stimulation of tau aggregate clearance are currently being studied as disease-modifying therapies for FTD-tau. Inhibition of TDP43 aggregation, stimulation of TDP43 aggregate clearance, boosting progranulin levels, activating the autophagy-lysosome system, or modification of the ubiquitin proteasome system are all therapeutic options for FTD-TDP (111). Despite these advancements, the pathophysiology and genetics of FTD remain unknown. Additional genetic pathways and loci connected to immunological dysregulation and inflammation have recently been found, leading to new potential therapeutic targets (112), in addition to recognized mutations in MAPT, GRN, and C9orf72 genes. Furthermore, identifying mutation carriers at the asymptomatic/preclinical level would allow researchers to try disease-modifying medicines at an early stage, when cognitive deficits may still be reversible (100).

To improve the odds of favorable outcomes in future treatment clinical trials, information gaps in the etiology and clinical characterisation of FTD must be filled, as well as the creation of accurate biomarkers and specialized evaluation methods. Desmarais and colleagues have thus developed a set of guidelines to help standardize future FTD clinical studies and increase the likelihood of favorable results (113-267).

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